

Harnessing Ocean Energy: Advancing Marine Renewable Technologies for Sustainable Coastal Development

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Abstract: Globally, the ocean contains a great deal of energy in many forms such as tidal, wave, salinity, and temperature changes between the deep sea and the surface. These vast amounts of energy have yet to be explored, thus there is a lot of potential for harnessing the aforementioned energies. The present investigation examines the methods and techniques of harnessing these energies by establishing Marine Renewable Technologies (MRTs) for long-term growth in coastal locations. Recent developments, including processes and issues in ocean energy technology, wave and tidal energy conversion mechanisms, and energy generation employing salinity gradients, are described. Meanwhile, economic feasibility and technical issues are addressed. Several important variables, including efficiency, reliability, financial considerations, and environmental factors, have been considered. Furthermore, the feasibility of blending these technologies with the current framework is assessed. The necessity of various rules and regulations for this task is also discussed in order to promote coastal growth, maintain marine life, and fulfill rising energy demand while lowering carbon footprint.

Keywords: Ocean Energy; Marine Renewable Technologies (MRTs); Sustainable Shore Development; Wave and Tidal Energy; Offshore Energy

1. Introduction

Electrical energy is always in high demand, both on land and on board. However, the use of fossil fuels contributes to increased carbon dioxide levels and, as a result, to climate change. The International Maritime Organization (IMO) has set a net-zero carbon objective for 2050, along with incremental checkpoints. This has instilled a sense of obligation to develop renewable energy. This is the ideal opportunity for a shift to alternate solutions for increased energy demands on board (White, J. K. 2024, Bello, U et al. 2021 & Hanspal, M. S.2024). Though improvements in solar and wind energy for power generation are very encouraging, the ocean has a large amount of untapped energy, particularly in coastal regions. Still, additional research is needed to capture such energy using MRTs in order to promote coastal growth (Wibisono, R. B 2024, Mehan, A. et al. 2023 & Koumentakos, A. G. 2019). In fact, the ocean serves as a reservoir of energy, containing wave energy, energy from varied tidal types, continuous current movement, temperature differences among ocean strata, and salinity differences between salt and freshwater. As a result, the ocean has an infinite supply of energy while being extremely clean and environmentally friendly. Therefore, if used properly, it might provide a sizable amount of energy for the maritime sector as well as for coastal development (Trenberth, K. E 2022). Unlike traditional high-carbon energy sources, ocean energy is almost always renewable and emits near-zero carbon. It may therefore fulfill the need for energy while also contributing to a clean environment. Such a change is critical for both environmental conservation and establishing a sustainable, promising future. Coastal regions are the largest space for the world population, making them particularly vulnerable to the detrimental consequences of climate change. This could result in excessive sea level rise, unpredictable weather events and other natural disasters that cause coastal erosion (Ruan, X et al. 2024). Such insights highlight the need for immediate strategic growth with an emphasis on environmental conservation. The above-mentioned issues can be addressed by creating energy from diverse ocean sources. These energies, particularly in coastal areas, have the potential to significantly boost economic growth while

also mitigating natural disasters (Mathew, J. T et al. 2025, Majumder, M. Z. H et al. 2024 & Chen, Q et al. 2025). This method of tapping energy can open the door for new enterprises to create such technologies while also creating job opportunities in coastal areas and increasing the prosperity of the coastal population (Boshell, F et al. 2020).

There are several chances to harness ocean-based energy, but equal impediments remain in the shape of advanced technology, capital and operational expenditures, and environmental protection until they are implemented (Jafarizadeh, H et al. 2024, Jamaledin, N et al. 2024 & Simbolon, R et al. 2024). An efficient, consistent, and reasonably priced MRT is essential to producing the desired amount of ocean energy. This necessitates a thorough examination into enhancing performance, endurance, and mature technology to withstand the abrasive and corrosive marine environment. In addition, encouraging laws and regulations to ensure the commercial sustainability of such advancements are critical. As previously stated in the literature, this effort involves multiple ocean energies in the form of new MRTs and associated bottlenecks. The study also looks into the financial sustainability of ocean energy, considering capital and operating costs, as well as possible revenue streams. While examining commercial expenses such as starting and operating costs, this study also investigates potential sources of income. This study investigates numerous approaches for integrating the proposed MRTs into the present facilities, as well as the establishment of long-term coastal growth. This study also emphasizes the need for regulations that make it easier for such unique technologies to arise, as well as the necessity to raise public knowledge about the use of such energy sources. International help and cooperation are also required to hasten the process of implementing such MRTs.

The paper's structure is outlined below: Section 2 gives an overview of several maritime energy resources. While, Section 4 focuses on the many elements, including cost analysis and regulatory hurdles to capturing ocean energy. Section 5 discusses environmental issues and finally, the last section presents an overview assessment of the preceding topics and makes the required suggestions.

2. Maritime Energy Resources: A primer

The marine renewable power, also referred to as marine and hydrokinetic power, is a renewable electricity source that is generated from the inherent motion of water, such as wave action, tides, and river & ocean currents. A method named Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion (OTEC) is another way to utilize marine energy from variances in temperature in water. There is an abundance of opportunities to utilize marine energy. The entirety of the usable marine energy prospective in Asia is substantial; however, it differs significantly by country and region due to variations in coastline length, oceanic conditions, and advances in technology. The total projected marine energy potential in Asia (techno-economically achievable) between 2010 and 2022, according to studies by several Indian and international authoritative sources, is 300 to 400 GW. India's tidal energy potential is projected to be roughly 10 GW, with important spots in the Gulf of Khambhat, Gulf of Kutch, and regions of the Sundarbans. The most promising places for wave energy in India are across the western coast, mainly in Kerala, Karnataka, and sections of Tamil Nadu, with a capacity of 40 GW. Global ocean thermal energy conversion is expected to be up to 180 GW, with India accounting for only 2 GW, largely in the Andaman and Nicobar Islands.

2.1 Wave, Tidal, and OTEC: A Global Snapshot of Technological and Regional Readiness

Based on the statistics and site details, techno-economically possible and conceivable marine energy contributes around 54 GW in India in 2022, whereas it accounts for 57% of total power generation in the United States in 2019. Even if just a fraction of this technical resource potential is achieved, maritime energy technologies will have a significant impact on global energy consumption. However, the availability of resources alone is insufficient to take a technology to the commercial level. Table 1. provides a comparative overview of marine renewable technologies, including wave, tidal, and OTEC. Table 1. is developed based on reports from agencies such as the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), the International Energy Agency (IEA), the United States Department of Energy, and the European Commission. Table 1 shows that Asia has enormous potential for wave and tidal energy, particularly around the coasts of India, Indonesia, and Japan, but OTEC remains mostly untapped due to a lack of proper warm water temperatures (excluding in Hawaii). It also demonstrates that Europe leads in market implementation, particularly in tidal energy in the United Kingdom and France. Wave energy is being developed, with many experimental projects in Portugal and Ireland. OTEC is currently in a developmental level. Furthermore, the United States has enormous prospects for wave energy throughout the Pacific coast (e.g., Oregon, California) and tidal energy in Alaska,

but OTEC remains restricted to exploratory initiatives in Hawaii.

Table 1. Regional Analysis of Wave, Tidal, and OTEC Technologies. TRL - Technology Readiness Level

Parameter	Asia	Europe	United States
Technological Maturity	Wave: Mid-stage (TRL 5–7) Tidal: Advanced (TRL 7–9) OTEC: Early-stage (TRL 3–5)	Wave: Mid-stage (TRL 5–7) Tidal: Advanced (TRL 7–9) OTEC: Early-stage (TRL 3–5)	Wave: Mid-stage (TRL 5–7) Tidal: Advanced (TRL 7–9) OTEC: Early-stage (TRL 3–5)
Status of deployment	Pilot & demo (India, Japan, Indonesia)	Pilot & demo (Portugal, UK, France)	Pilot plants (Oregon, Alaska)
	Limited Commercial Tidal	Commercial Tidal (France, UK)	Commercial Tidal (Alaska)
Accessibility of Resources	High		
	India, Indonesia, Philippines, Japan, South Korea	UK, Ireland, France, Portugal, Ireland	<i>Pacific Coast, Alaska</i>
Top Nations	India, Indonesia, Japan, South Korea, Philippines	UK, France, Portugal, Ireland	US (Oregon, Alaska, Hawaii); limited EU activity
Environmental Implications	Moderate (localized, with minimal emissions)		
Potential for Energy	Wave: 170–250 GW (Asia-wide) Tidal: 100–120 GW	Wave: 100 GW (EU-wide) Tidal: 20–25 GW	Wave: 64 GW (US-wide) Tidal: 12 GW
Required Infrastructure	Converters, offshore moorings, and grids	Barrages, tidal stream turbines, and grid connectivity	Deep sea pipes, tidal turbines, and buoys
Policy Assistance	Moderate to strong (India, Japan, South Korea, China); Limited for OTEC	Strong in EU (UK, France, Portugal)	Growing support (DOE, WA State, Hawaii)
Business viability	Improving but still not lucrative	Successful in specialized markets (France, UK)	R&D is still underway (especially in Hawaii)
Opportunities for Development	High (particularly for wave and OTEC potential)	High (major EU investments, particularly Tidal)	Moderate (growth in wave, limited in OTEC)

Despite the abundance of resources, MRTs' practical applicability are severely limited by their low TRL. Asia and the United States are prime examples, demonstrating that the existence of resources alone will not result in widespread use of such energy until technology matures. This point is particularly prominent in Europe, where tidal power supplies are limited but commercially profitable due to high TRL. In contrast, tropical regions with strong temperature gradients were unable to successfully implement OETC. As a result, in addition to possessing adequate maritime resources, only technological improvements can help to maximize the utilization of available marine resources.

3. New Marine Renewable Energy Technologies

According to the preceding sections, contemporary MRTs primarily use electrical energy from waves, tides, and OETC. This section will provide a brief overview of the stated technologies. Figure 1 depicts a peek of energy generation using such resources

Figure 1. Various Ocean Energy Technologies (Bianchi, M. et al. 2024).

3.1. Wave Energy

Waves form when the wind interacts with the water's surface (due to temperature differences caused by the sun). The energy potential for waves is maximum between 30° and 60° latitude across both hemispheres on the west coast because of the worldwide orientation of the wind. As the waves progress, their dimensions increase. Wave Energy Converters (WECs) are used to extract energy from waves. There are seven common types of such converters: attenuators, point absorbers, pressure differentials, oscillating water columns, overtopping, and oscillating wave surge converters. The variety of these models is caused by differences in wave resources across locations and distances from the coast. Surface attenuators often feature many floating segments bonded to each other and aligned parallel to incoming waves. They employ the rise and fall of swells to generate a flexing action which can be turned into spinning or used to operate hydraulic pumps that produce power. Point absorbers take energy from the relative motion of a moving body responding to wave forcing and stationary or stagnant structures. The moving body can be situated on the surface or submerged, while the 'fixed' body could be the seabed or a different structure that is less impacted by wave movement. They are smaller in proportion to the length of the waves from which they obtain energy. This energy can be converted to electricity using a linear or rotational generator, or it can be utilized to pump the fluid directly. An oscillating column of water is used to harness the wave motion and create sufficient air pressure in the chamber using an air turbine. Air is drawn back through the turbine and into the chamber by the vacuum created as the water leaves the chamber. They can be found ashore or in deeper water offshore. Electricity can be generated by coupling the turbine to a rotary generator. Overtopping devices are lengthy structures which enable wave motion to raise a reservoir's water level above the surrounding ocean. Similar to traditional hydropower, energy is generated by forcing fluid through a low-head turbine connected to a generator due to the pressure differential between the reservoir's water and the surface water. The Oscillating Wave Surge Converter has two ends, one of which is hinged to the structure or seabed and the other of which is free to move. The horizontal motion of the wave surge causes relative motion of the body, resulting in energy being created and converted to electricity via a generator. Figure 2. depicts the described wave energy technologies.

Figure 2. Classification of Wave Energy Conversion Systems.

3.2. Tidal Energy

Tidal energy has an extensive past, with cultures living along the shore using it for a variety of purposes decades ago. The first tidal power station was built in France (La Rance Tidal Power Station) in the middle of the twentieth century, and it is now the second largest station in operation, with a capacity of 240 MW. South Korea's Sihwa Lake Tidal Power Station is the world's largest tidal power station, with an installed capacity of 254 MW and ten turbines. Tidal and wave energy differ mostly in their source. The wind interacts with the ocean surface to generate wave energy, whereas gravitational forces provide tidal energy. Furthermore, the technology employed to harness each type of energy vary. Though waves and tides are sometimes used interchangeably, there is a distinct difference between the two. Tides are large waves that cause the sea to rise and fall near the shore. They exist as a result of the gravitational pull of the moon and sun. Their size varies with regard to the ocean as the planet revolves on its axis. In terms of tides, the moon has a greater influence than the sun because it is much closer to Earth.

The moon's gravitational pull causes four tides per day. However, local topography and ocean conditions can create minor differences. This typical pattern is known as the semi-diurnal tidal cycle, which has two high tides and two low tides every day, or a period of 12 hours and 25 minutes. This kind is common along Atlantic beaches. Parts of the Gulf of Mexico exhibit a diurnal rhythm with one high and one low tide every day. A mixed variety with two unequally high and low tides every day is also possible, as seen on the Pacific Coast of the United States. Tidal energy technology utilizes the potential or kinetic energy of moving water during tide flow using tidal barrages, tidal stream turbines, or innovative ways such as dynamic tidal power. This is commonly employed in coastal areas with a broad range of tides, such as France, the United Kingdom, and South Korea, because it is highly predictable. Despite the fact that environmental and geographical impacts must be addressed/regulated, the technology is established and thus reliable.

Tidal stream generating is similar to regular wind turbines in that it uses the fluid's kinetic energy to produce electricity. As the name suggests, a tidal stream generator involves placing a tidal turbine or other comparable technology inside the tidal flow, or stream of flowing water. The movement of volume of water works on the harvesting system, transferring energy. Tidal stream generating is similar to regular wind turbines in that it uses the fluid's kinetic energy to produce electricity. As the name suggests, a tidal stream generator involves placing a tidal turbine or other comparable technology inside the tidal flow, or stream of flowing water. The moving volume of water works on the harvesting system, transferring energy. Axial turbines, oscillating hydrofoils, crossflow turbines, and/or tidal kite systems are some of the standard models of tidal stream generators. Figure 3. illustrates a few of these technologies.

Figure 3. Illustrative Examples of Tidal Energy Conversion Technologies.

3.3. Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion (OTEC)

OTEC is one of the renewables that uses the temperature difference between surface water (hot) and deep water (cold) to generate electricity. A temperature differential of 20 degrees Celsius drives a turbine and develop usable energy. The world's first OTEC plant was erected in Matanzas Bay, Cuba, in 1930, with an open cycle model with a gross capacity of 22 kW that was not commercially feasible. Later, in 1979, an even more advanced closed-cycle OTEC plant known as Mini-OTEC was built off the coast of Hawaii, with a gross capacity of 50 kW and a closed-cycle system, becoming the first to generate net power at sea. To create energy, an OTEC facility must continuously use enormous amounts of hot and cold water. A 100 MW OTEC plant will use approximately 10-20 billion gallons of water each day.

OTEC systems are classified into several types, the most common of which are open-cycle and closed- cycle systems. A hybrid system is also available. Seawater serves various functions in the open cycle, including heat source, working fluid, coolant, and heat sink. Warm surface water gets to an evaporator, where it is quickly vaporized to steam in particle vacuum. A vacuum pump maintains low pressure in the evaporator. The low pressure helps in removing non-condensable gasses from the evaporator. The steam and water mixture from the evaporator then enter a turbine, which drives it and creates energy. The turbine exhaust is combined with cold water from the deep ocean in a direct contact condenser and released into the ocean. This cycle is then replicated. The cycle is described as 'open' since the condensate gets released into the ocean.

In a closed cycle, an operating fluid other than water is employed, such as ammonia, propane, or Freon. The warm surface water is transported to a boiler via pump. This hot water transfers its heat to the secondary working fluid, shedding energy, and gets released again at the ocean's surface. The vapors from the secondary working fluid produced in the boiler move a turbine, which generates power. The turbine effluent is cooled in a surface condenser using cold deep seawater and then fed back to the boiler via a pump. Warm, surface seawater enters a vacuum chamber in the hybrid cycle ocean thermal energy conversion process and is flash-evaporated into steam. The steam is utilized to evaporate a working fluid having a low boiling point, which subsequently powers a turbine to produce energy. The open-cycle is most suited for offshore installation, while the closed- cycle is best suited for onshore installation. However, both open-cycle and closed-cycle OTEC systems can be erected onshore. This technology is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. OTEC Technologies.

3.4. Salinity Gradient Energy

Another method for producing energy is through a salinity gradient. This employs salt concentration changes between saltwater (sea) and freshwater (river) to create a pressure difference.

Figure 5. Key Technologies for Electricity Generation from Salinity Gradient Energy

This commonly occurs when a river flows into the sea. Saltwater will have a higher osmotic pressure than freshwater. The pressure differential is used to generate electricity. Many ways are being explored for such technology, with two of the most popular being reverse electro-dialysis (RED) and pressure retarded osmosis (PRO). The first approach entails building a salt battery in which ions are transported across membrane to generate energy, while the latter involves pumping freshwater through a semipermeable membrane into a seawater pressurized chamber. Increased pressure causes the turbine to revolve, resulting in the generation of electricity (Reyes-Mendoza. et al.2020).

RED produces energy through the regulated amalgamation of two water bodies with varying salinities (Sampedro, T. et al. 2024). This approach employs several anion and cation exchange members organized to create low and high salinity compartments (Guo, X et al. 2025). When freshwater and saltwater are injected into these membranes, opposite charges flow through the appropriate ions (cation, anion, etc.), resulting in electricity, just like an electric battery. PRO turns the osmotic pressure of the salt solution into hydraulic pressure, which drives the turbine and generates power (Pan, J. et al. 2024). As with RED, this technology takes advantage of the difference in saline concentration between fresh and salt water (Huang, Y. et al. 2025). Figure 5. Depicts prominent methods of creating electricity using salient gradient energy.

3.5. Technical and Functional Limitations

Even though various technologies are available for maritime renewables, there are still technical and functional limitations. Different structures are utilized in wave energy conversion technology; however, they are still in their early phases when compared to other renewable technologies such as wind and solar, and technological readiness must mature (Aderinto, T., & Li, H. 2018). The design, operation, and deployment of Wind Energy Converter (WEC) structures in the ocean environment presents a unique challenge relative to land-based systems. WEC's design requires it to interact with sea waves in order to extract energy from them. So, the problem is more severe. In addition to withstanding load changes during operation, the structure should be able to withstand major hurricanes, tsunamis, and other natural ocean catastrophes. Seawater is corrosive in nature, which may affect a few or several components of WEC. During the design phase, a detailed plan for operating and maintaining such a system must be developed. This is bound to raise the operational and maintenance costs. Another important factor to consider when planning a WEC system is location or accessibility, particularly if it is offshore. Construction issues are less common in coastal and nearshore WECs than in deep offshore WECs. This will improve accessibility as well. However, WEC constructions built near the shore have to cope with other regular coastal activities. Furthermore, the devices' accessibility for deployment and maintenance operations is critical in choosing the right technology, as performing maintenance at sea is both costly and unsafe (Tiron, R et al. 2015). The period for scheduling maintenance is difficult to determine because of incidents such as corrosion, wave stresses, and biofouling. Furthermore, deployment and maintenance activities necessitate sufficiently lengthy, consecutive time intervals in which the sea state is adequately calm. A balance between scheduling and doing maintenance should exist.

The majority of design and operational issues apply to tidal energy conversion systems as well. That is, the primary issues to be addressed are consistency, resilience, and installation (Segura, E et al. 2017). Furthermore, resource mapping for tidal energy currently lacks resolution and variety. Other peripheral and controlling components, such as power electronics, generators, gearboxes, and moorings, are to be enhanced alongside the core structure. New non-corrosive materials have to be employed to extend the plant's life.

The first and most significant problem in OTEC technology is the minimal temperature differential, which leads to reduced efficiency (Nakib, T.H et al. 2025). Even in tropical locations, the temperature differential between heat source and sink is typically 20 to 25 degrees Celsius, which is extremely low in comparison to other thermodynamic systems. Even under optimal conditions, the efficiency remains poor. However, using the appropriate working fluid and cycle can help to improve efficiency. Therefore, the design must prioritize these factors in accordance with capacity and application. The heat exchanger plays a critical role in the proper operation of the OTEC. In reality, the heat exchanger transmits heat from the hot surface to the working fluid. The rate at which this is accomplished has a significant impact on the overall efficiency of the system. So, parameters such as the number of heat exchanger plates/tubes, pressure drop, and heat flow rate/ heat transfer coefficient must be tuned to achieve promising outcomes.

The choice or mix of working fluids should be based on thermal efficiency, safety at work, and operational feasibility, as both the working fluid and the thermal cycle influence the system's total performance. In a few circumstances, alternate fluids/mix work effectively, but in others, they add complexity and handling dangers.

The evolution of the salinity gradient energy system began more than six decades ago, but it has struggled to gain traction due to poor real-time performance when compared to other renewable forms of energy (Essalhi, M et al. 2023). Hydrodynamic and mass transmission restrictions exist; however, these can be solved in the modern day with novel materials and careful design. While significant power density can be achieved in lab case tests with rigorously constant solution concentration, the practical energy conversion efficiency is not promising (Rastgar, M. et al.2023). Furthermore, this system has low stability and should be

addressed through alternate process design.

Biofouling is an acute issue in all ocean energy structures. It is described as the undesired formation of a microbial layer on the surfaces, which then leads to the infestation of submerged objects by fixing organisms. It grows over time into a glue-like biofilm that allows all bacterial species to attach to and proliferate. These biofilms are difficult to get rid of, reducing the overall performance of the system. This problem can be solved with appropriate ant biofouling techniques.

4. Ocean Energy: Costs and Constraints

While the technical and operational limits were addressed in the previous part, this section discusses the economic limitations. According to our earlier explanation, any enhanced design, technical novelty, maintenance, and parameter control during operation will all increase the system's cost.

At the design stage, planning for seamless operation of WEC requires an integrated operating and maintenance strategy, which incurs substantial lifecycle costs. The return on investment or payback period could be longer. The entire cost of a tidal energy system is determined by empirical data costs, significant changes in project cost approach, and location-specific costs. The different components of this are dynamic in nature, as is the overall cost. The technology is still in the development stage and has yet to be widely implemented. This may also be the cause for the high cost of tidal energy.

The majority of ocean energy structures require significant money and longer time to construct. Tidal energy technologies continue to pose significant risks in terms of cost and revenue, as well as to investors and insurers. Banks prefer to provide loans to low-risk short-term initiatives over high-risk long-term enterprises. To attain affordable prices in the near future, appealing incentives must be created to promote the development of the maritime energy sector.

For an OTEC system, the plant's size and location are critical to the entire budget. If the facility is built relatively close to the shore, the transmission costs could be significantly lowered. Furthermore, the cost of a certain heat exchanger, working fluid, or heat cycle may vary depending on the application, and each has a unique overall cost. If we want higher performance from this technology, we must make a trade-off between economy and output. The number of components in salinity gradients varies depending on the kind and the cost. The control of parameters and the necessity for greater maintenance raise the overall cost. Developing new regulations in support of ocean energy, creating incentives, and relaxing the procedures for selecting a site and simplifying the rules will assist not only improve marine energy but also significantly reduce overall costs.

5. Environmental Impacts of Ocean Energy

Potential environmental dangers of these developments include habitat damage, water flow patterns, electromagnetic radiation, and noise in aquatic settings. Ocean researchers must do rigorous testing prior to and following approval to ensure low dangers in those regions. The main challenge that arises in the sea environment is hydrodynamics. The severe wave pattern and repeatability of such occurrences must be analyzed using appropriate tools, such as CFD, to estimate the strong temporal variability, and the site may be chosen accordingly. Long-term wave climates at the locations that are relevant should also be addressed for analysis in order to lessen wave stress. Negative impacts of ocean energy structure include loss of ecosystems and degrading. The impacts vary depending on submerged surfaces, above-water platforms, and seabed changes. There is also a possibility that native or migratory marine species will become snagged or collide with the unit. Furthermore, it could affect the local flow and cause the relocation or diversion of larvae, spores, fish, and even marine animals, especially in large-scale installations. Some constructions release harmful fluids or paints into the surroundings. Perhaps the most serious environmental issues raised by OTEC systems is the chemical and thermal change of saltwater. The degassing activity may possess a negative effect on the quality of the local air, especially in locations near major OTEC facilities.

6. Conclusion

Marine renewable energy includes the extraction of electrical power through the motion of ocean waters, such as currents or waves, as well as temperature and salinity differential. This energy is the most unexplored kind of energy and remains in its infancy, but with great potential for producing energy in a more

environmentally friendly manner, minimizing carbon footprints. The advancements in wave energy conversion assessment approaches have been highly positive, since sophisticated computer software and apps are now accessible to foresee and model wave conditions at higher temporal and geographical resolutions. Tidal energy has significant potential to generate clean electricity in the medium and long future. Still, challenges such as cost-effectiveness, dependability, operational safety, site selection, environmental concerns, and longevity must be addressed through careful design and the use of novel materials in order to maximize the potential of tidal energy. The involvement of heat exchangers, working fluid, heat cycle, and turbine is critical in OTEC, and the parameters must be tuned to achieve optimal performance. The scientific and commercial problems remain for salinity gradient energy technology, which has the highest cost and is still not working as predicted in real time. All of these technologies raise at least a few environmental concerns that must be addressed. Furthermore, legal issues such as site approval, loan lending, and strict laws restrict the system's growth. Rules and regulations must be standardized, and incentives for such efforts will make ocean energy extraction both promising and inexpensive. This paper provides an in-depth analysis of several MRTs, as well as technological, operational, economic, and environmental challenges. A few ideas are also provided to help MRTs grow.

References

- Aderinto, T., & Li, H. (2018). Ocean Wave Energy Converters: Status and Challenges. *Energies*, 11(5), 1250. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11051250>
- Backoffice-Cms. (n.d.). OES | Ocean Energy Systems - an IEA Technology Collaboration Programme. <https://www.ocean-energy-systems.org/>
- Bello, U., Livingstone, U., Abdullahi, A. M., Sulaiman, I., & Yahuza, K. M. (2021). Renewable energy transition: a panacea to the ravaging effects of climate change in Nigeria. *Aceh International Journal of Science and Technology*, 10(3), 182-195.
- Bianchi, M., & Fernandez, I. F. (2024). A systematic methodology to assess local economic impacts of ocean renewable energy projects: Application to a tidal energy farm. *Renewable Energy*, 221, 119853. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.119853>
- Boshell, F., Hecke, J., & Salgado, A. (2020). *Innovation Outlook: Ocean Energy Technologies*. IRENA: Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates.
- Chen, Q., & Yin, X. (2025). Sustainable Coastal Energy Development: Integrated Modeling of Renewable Energy Sources for Optimal Economic and Environmental Performance. *Energy*, 134504. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2025.134504>
- Essalhi, M., Avcı, A. H., Lipnizki, F., & Tavajohi, N. (2023). The potential of salinity gradient energy based on natural and anthropogenic resources in Sweden. *Renewable Energy*, 215, 118984. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.118984>
- Guo, X., Liu, W., Feng, Q., Yuan, Z., Chen, L., Xiao, K., & Teng, C. (2025). Nanofluidic ion transport and osmotic energy conversion based on all-natural kelp membranes. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 512, 162363. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccej.2025.162363>
- Hanspal, M. S. (2024). IMPACT OF INDIAN ENERGY POLICY ON ENVIRONMENT AND CLIMATE CHANGE: LEGAL AND POLICY INSIGHTS. Available at SSRN 5095182.
- Huang, Y., Shen, P., Ma, Q., Li, W. Y., Ma, N., Wang, X., ... & Zhu, M. (2025). A general approach of reinforcing hydrogels for salinity-gradient energy harvesting. *Nano Energy*, 138, 110898. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2025.110898>
- Jafarizadeh, H., Yamini, E., Zolfaghari, S. M., Esmailion, F., Assad, M. E. H., & Soltani, M. (2024). Navigating challenges in large-scale renewable energy storage: Barriers, solutions, and innovations. *Energy Reports*, 12, 2179-2192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyr.2024.08.019>
- Jamaleddin, N., Gabr, M., Borden, R., Argall, R., & Lasser, D. (2024). Numerical study on micropile group behavior supporting fixed bottom marine hydrokinetic devices in sandy seabed. *Ocean Engineering*, 293, 116614. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2023.116614>
- Koumentakos, A. G. (2019). Developments in Electric and Green Marine Ships. *Applied System Innovation*, 2(4), 34. <https://doi.org/10.3390/asi2040034>
- Majumder, M. Z. H., Shampa, M. T. A., Islam, M. A., Deowan, S. A., & Hafiz, F. (2024). Marine renewable energy harnessing for sustainable development in Bangladesh: A technological review. *Energy Reports*, 11, 1342-1362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyr.2024.01.001>
- Mathew, J. T., Inobeme, A., Etsuyankpa, B. M., Adetunji, C. O., Tanko, M. S., Abdullahi, A., ... & Dolapo, I. (2025). Potential of Marine Resources for Generation of Clean and Green Energy: A Path Towards Sustainable Future. In *Biomass Valorization: A Sustainable Approach towards Carbon Neutrality and Circular Economy* (pp. 293-313). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-8557-5_13
- Mehan, A., & Casey, Z. S. (2023). Blue Infrastructures: An Exploration of Oceanic Networks and Urban–Industrial–Energy Interactions in the Gulf of Mexico. *Sustainability*, 15(18), 13699. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151813699>

- Nakib, T.H., Hasanuzzaman, M., Rahim, N.A. et al. Global challenges of ocean thermal energy conversion and its prospects: a review. *J. Ocean Eng. Mar. Energy* 11, 197–231 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40722-024-00368-4>
- Pan, J., Xu, W., Zhang, Y., Ke, Y., Dong, J., Li, W., ... & Xia, F. (2024). Osmotic Energy-Based Systems for Self-Powered Sensing. *Nano Energy*, 110412. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2024.110412>
- Rastgar, M., Moradi, K., Burroughs, C., Hemmati, A., Hoek, E., & Sadrzadeh, M. (2023). Harvesting blue energy based on salinity and temperature gradient: challenges, solutions, and opportunities. *Chemical Reviews*, 123(16), 10156–10205. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.3c00168>
- Reyes-Mendoza, O., Alvarez-Silva, O., Chiappa-Carrara, X., Enriquez, C., (2020). Variability of the thermohaline structure of a coastal hypersaline lagoon and the implications for salinity gradient energy harvesting. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, 38 (100645). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2020.100645>
- Ruan, X., Sun, H., Shou, W., & Wang, J. (2024). The impact of climate change and urbanization on compound flood risks in coastal areas: a comprehensive review of methods. *Applied Sciences*, 14(21), 10019. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app142110019>
- Sampedro, T., Mazo, E., Gómez-Coma, L., Arruti, A., Fallanza, M., Pinedo, J., ... & Ortiz, I. (2024). Harnessing salinity gradient energy: Pushing forward in water reclamation via on-site reverse electrodialysis technology. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 371, 123251. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.123251>
- Segura, E., Morales, R., Somolinos, J. A., & López, A. (2017). Techno-economic challenges of tidal energy conversion systems: Current status and trends. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 77, 536–550. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.04.054>
- Simbolon, R., Sihotang, W., & Sihotang, J. (2024). Tapping Ocean Potential: Strategies for integrating tidal and wave energy into national power grids. *GEMOY: Green Energy Management and Optimization Yields*, 1(1), 49-65. <https://pubcenter.ristek.or.id/index.php/Gemoy/article/view/38>
- Tidal Currents - Currents: NOAA's National Ocean Service Education. (n.d.). https://oceanservice.noaa.gov/education/tutorial_currents/02tidal1.html. Accessed 10 February 2025
- Tiron, R., Mallon, F., Dias, F., & Reynaud, E. G. (2015). The challenging life of wave energy devices at sea: A few points to consider. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 43, 1263–1272. <https://doi:10.1016/j.rser.2014.11.105>
- Trenberth, K. E. (2022). *The changing flow of energy through the climate system*. Cambridge University Press.
- White, J. K. (2024). *The Truth about Energy: Our Fossil-fuel Addiction and the Transition to Renewables*. Cambridge.
- Wibisono, R. B. (2024). YOUTH-GOVERNMENT COLLABORATION IN MARITIME DEVELOPMENT: A PATHWAY TO A SUSTAINABLE JAKARTA. *Jurnal Kebijakan Pemerintahan*, 61-85.